

Evaluation of Tzanakis Score in Acute Appendicitis among Indian Patients**Abhishek Prasad¹, Arunkumar Chawan², Roshani Damor³, Pogaku Sai Sharan⁴,
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Abstract:**Aim:** This study is aimed to detect the efficacy of Tzanakis scoring system in diagnosing acute appendicitis in our set up using histopathology as the gold standard.**Materials and Methods:** This cross-sectional validation study was carried out in ESIC Medical College & Hospital, Kalaburagi from October 2023 to October 2024, after approval from the Ethics Committee of the Hospital. The study included all adult patients of either gender who presented with clinical findings suggestive of acute appendicitis, who were assigned Tzanakis score pre-operatively and who subsequently underwent emergency appendectomy with histological examination of the resected specimens.**Result:** Sensitivity of Tzanakis score in diagnosing acute appendicitis was 91.3%, specificity 57.14%, positive predictive value 93.33%, negative predictive value 50% and diagnostic accuracy was 86.79%. The area under the curve (AUC) of the receiver operator characteristic (ROC) curve for the Tzanakis scoring system was 0.742, with a standard error of 0.083, 95% confidence interval- 0.579 – 0.906, p value = 0.004.**Conclusion:** This study concluded that the Tzanakis scoring system is acceptable for diagnosing acute appendicitis.**Keywords:** Tzanakis score, sensitivity and specificity, acute appendicitis, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, diagnostic accuracy.

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Introduction

Acute appendicitis (AA) is a common cause for a visit to the emergency department and appendectomy represents the most commonly performed emergency procedure in surgery. [1] The incidence of appendicitis is approximately 233 per 100,000 population per year, with a lifetime incidence risk ranging from 6.7 to 8.6%. [2] Appendicitis is most common between the ages of 10 and 20 years, but no age is exempt. [3]

Acute appendicitis is caused by the obstruction of the appendiceal lumen, leading to rapid bacterial multiplication, inflammation, ischemia, distension of the appendix and ultimately perforation and the risk of perforation increases by 5% in every subsequent 12 hours period after 36 hours have passed since the onset of symptoms. This suggests the need for expedient diagnosis and treatment. Mortalities associated with appendicitis are associated with perforation and subsequent progression in to systemic infections. [4] AA is heralded by pain to the right lower quadrant. This

might be accompanied by nausea, vomiting and signs of systematic inflammatory response like fever and chills. Besides, blood chemistry might indicate elevated acute phase proteins like C-reactive protein (CRP) and high white blood count (WBC). These findings are however not specific for AA. In fact, pain to the right lower quadrant with systemic signs of inflammation and elevated inflammatory markers in blood might be due to a number of pathologies, especially bowel pathologies including right sided colitis, ileitis or gastroenteritis. The spectrum of possible differential diagnosis even gets wider in female patients in reproductive age. [5]

Despite advances in diagnosis, acute appendicitis still shows morbidity of approximately 10% and mortality of approximately 1-5%. [6] According to available statistics, one out of every five cases of appendicitis is misdiagnosed whereas negative appendectomy rate is 15%–40% in patients who undergo emergency appendectomy. [7] Negative

appendectomy carries a significant post-operative morbidity. At present there is no single perfect diagnostic test for acute appendicitis. [8] Because of fear of the consequences of delayed or missed diagnosis, the indication for surgery for suspected AA is liberally made, resulting in high rates of negative ppendectomy. [5] There is need for a better preoperative screening of patients with suspected appendicitis.

A number of scoring systems have been devised to help in the diagnosis of appendicitis. Alvarado and the modified Alvarado scores are the two most commonly used scoring systems but these systems are mainly dependent upon clinical evaluation and white blood cell count alone and do not employ any radiological investigation. About 20-33% of the patients having acute appendicitis present with atypical clinical and laboratory findings, requiring the use of some imaging modality to help solve the diagnostic dilemma. [9] Abdominal Ultrasonography is an inexpensive, readily available and non-invasive method with an accuracy rate of upto 71%–90% for the diagnosis of acute appendicitis. [10] Ultrasound is also a very helpful modality in ruling out other causes of acute abdomen and can accomplish more than CT scans.

The Tzanakis scoring system is a quantitative combination of the clinical evaluation with Ultrasound imaging and a marker of inflammatory response, which may enhance the diagnostic accuracy for subjects with suspected AA especially in geographical areas where CT scanning is not readily available on a 24-hour basis. [11] We conducted this study to detect the efficacy of Tzanakis scoring system in diagnosing acute appendicitis in our set up using histopathology as the gold standard.

Materials and Methods

This cross-sectional validation study was carried out in ESIC Medical College & Hospital, Kalaburagi from October 2023 to October 2024, after approval from the Ethics Committee of the Hospital. The study included all adult patients of either gender who presented with clinical findings suggestive of acute appendicitis, who were assigned Tzanakis score pre-operatively and who subsequently underwent emergency appendectomy with histological examination of the resected specimens. The Tzanakis score was developed by Nikolaos Tzanakis and colleagues in 2005 in a quest for a cost-effective tool for pre-operative diagnosis of acute appendicitis. The variables of Tzanakis scoring system were: Ultrasound positive for acute appendicitis (6 points), tenderness in the right lower abdominal

quadrant (4 points), rebound tenderness (3 points) and a leukocyte count of $\geq 12,000/L$ (2 points). We considered a cut off of ≥ 8 as highly suggestive of acute appendicitis. We compared the Tzanakis score to histological examination which is the Gold Standard for confirming the diagnosis of acute appendicitis.

Abdominal ultrasonography was performed by an ultrasonographer using Philips HD3 brand with a linear 6 MHz probe. We considered ultrasonography positive if any four of the following were present; (i) aperistaltic non-compressible blind ended sausage shaped structure arising from the base of the cecum, (ii) Distinct appendiceal wall layers, (iii) an appendiceal outer diameter greater than 6 mm, (iv) a target appearance of the appendix, (v) peri-appendicular fluid collection, (vi) echogenic prominent pericecal fat. Venous blood samples for white cell count were drawn by venepuncture in the left cubital fossa.

All the patients received standard emergency pre-operative management with nil by mouth status, intravenous fluids and Metronidazole, and systemic analgesics. All patients were subsequently treated with appendectomy via Grid iron incision. Operative findings were recorded and the resected specimens were sent for histopathological examination. Tzanakis score was correlated with the histopathology. The data were recorded on proforma and subjected to statistical analysis to measure the objective.

Statistical analysis

Data analysis was performed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY). The sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predicative values and overall diagnostic accuracy were calculated with their 95% confidence intervals using 2 x 2 table. There was no blinding. Categorical variables were presented as frequency and percentage and compared using the Chi-square test. The area under the curve (AUC) was calculated by plotting the receiver operator characteristic (ROC) curve.

Results

Out of a total of 106 patients, 60% (n=64) were males while 40% (n=42) were females, with the male: female ratio being 1.5:1. The age ranged from 9-56 years, with a mean \pm SD of 28.06 ± 10.9 years. 34 % patients were in the third decade of life, 26 % patients were in the second decade of life and 23 % patients were in the fourth decade of life. The age and gender-wise distribution is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Age and gender-wise distribution

Age groups, years	Females		Males		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
1-10	0	0.00%	2	3.13%	2	1.89%
11-20	10	23.81%	18	28.13%	28	26.42%
21-30	16	38.10%	20	31.25%	36	33.96%
31-40	11	26.19%	13	20.31%	24	22.64%
41-50	4	9.52%	8	12.50%	12	11.32%
51-60	1	2.38%	3	4.69%	4	3.77%
Total	42	100 %	64	100 %	106	100%

Positive cases of acute appendicitis on histopathology were 111 and Tzanakis score diagnosed 109 cases of acute appendicitis. True positive was 84, false positive 6, false negative 8, and true negative were 8 (Table-2).

Sensitivity of Tzanakis score in diagnosing acute appendicitis was 91.3%, specificity 57.14%, positive predictive value 93.33%, negative

predictive value 50% and diagnostic accuracy was 86.79% (Table-3). The receiver operator characteristics (ROC) curve was drawn showing good diagnostic accuracy of Tzanakis score for acute appendicitis (figure 1). The area under the curve (AUC) for the Tzanakis scoring system was 0.742, with a standard error of 0.083, 95% confidence interval- 0.579 – 0.906, p value = 0.004.

Diagonal segments are produced by ties.

Figure 1: ROC Curve

Based on the Tzanakis scoring system, out of 106 patients (N= 106), 84 (97.24%) were found to have histopathology-proven acute appendicitis (true positive), and 8 (7.54%) were histopathology true

negative (Table 2). Acute appendicitis was significantly high (Odd's ratio 14, 95% confidence interval 3.88-50.50, p-value = 0.00) in patients with a Tzanakis score of 8 or more.

Table 2: Comparison of Tzanakis score and histopathology using 2 x2 table (n=106)

		Histopathology of Appendix		
		Inflamed Appendix	Normal Appendix	
Tzanakis score	>8	True positive (a) (84)	False Positive (b) (6)	90
	< 8	False Negative (c) (8)	True Negative (d) (8)	16
	Total	92	14	106

Table 3: Statistical analysis of Tzanakis score

Statistical Parameter		Results
Sensitivity	$a/(a+c) \times 100$	91.3%
Specificity	$d/(b+d) \times 100$	57.14%
Positive Predictive Value	$a/(a+b) \times 100$	93.33%
Negative Predictive Value	$d/(c+d) \times 100$	50%
Diagnostic Accuracy	$a+d/a+b+c+d \times 100$	86.79%

Discussion

Among the common causes of abdominal emergencies, acute appendicitis ranks at the top, particularly in the young population. Atypical clinical presentations impose diagnostic dilemmas which have led to devise different scoring systems, imaging modalities, and laparoscopy and laboratory tests to help in making the diagnosis. While negative appendectomy is not uncommon, the risk of appendicular perforation is substantial if the diagnosis is missed or delayed. The study evaluated the diagnostic efficacy of the Tzanakis scoring system for acute appendicitis considering the histopathological finding as the gold standard. [12]

A total of 106 patients were recruited in our study. Majority of the patients were in the third decade of life, followed by second decade of life. A high distribution in the second and third decade of life was observed in several studies. (B, BL, Choudhary Singh, Iftikhar, Shashikala, Kathula, Patel, V, Saleem) As in our study, male preponderance has been reported by several other studies. However, a female predominance has also been reported by a couple of studies. (Singh, Patel). Statistical analysis

of the data revealed that Tzanakis score has 91.3% sensitivity and 57.14% specificity in diagnosing acute appendicitis. It also has positive predictive value of 93.33%, negative predictive value of 50% and diagnostic accuracy of 86.79% for diagnosing acute appendicitis.

Tzanakis et al. [11] have originally reported a sensitivity and specificity of 95.4% and 97.4% respectively with their scoring system. As per our study, sensitivity of Tzanakis scoring system was 91.3% which is comparable to Tzanakis et al. However, specificity of Tzanakis score in our study was low as compared to that described by Tzanakis et al. [11]

Several studies from the Indian sub-continent have compared the Tzanakis Score with either Alvarado Score or modified Alvarado score. The statistical parameters reported by these studies are given in Table 4. Most of the studies have reported that the Tzanakis Score is superior to the Alvarado score. An exception to this was a study by Lamture et al. in Maharashtra which reported that the Tzanakis scoring system had a lower value in diagnosing acute appendicitis in Indian populations.

Table 4:

Study	Sample size	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	Diagnostic accuracy	Negative appendectomy
Tzanakis et al. (original study)	303	95.4	97.4				
Anupriya et al.	70	65.52	100	100	37.5	71.43	-
Aravind et al.	420	86.95	75	97.5	33.33	-	
Bharath B et al.	100	50.57	92.31	97.78	21.82	56	
BL Y et al.	60	87	50	96	22	85	
Choudhary et al.	100	83.72	78.57	96	44	-	14
Singh et al.	100	91.58	80	98.9	33.3	91	-
Iftikhar et al.	60	94.11	88.88	97.95	72.72	93.33	2.04
Iqbal et al.	214	99	91	99	91		10.3
Shashikala et al.	50	59.09	33.33	86.6	10	-	-
Kathula et al.	30	95.7	85.7	95.7	85.7	-	-
Makor et al.	160	100	64	97	100	98	3
Patel et al.	96	94.44	83.33	98.8	50	-	-
Sharma & Kalaburgi	100	80.6	100	100	41.3	-	-
Malla and Batajoo	200	86.9	75	97.5	33.3	-	-
Sidgel et al.	100	91.48	66.66			90	6
Datta et al.	200	79.6	83	97	35.5	-	2
Saleem et al.	158	91.9	85.1	93.6	81.6	89.9	

Malik et al.	146	98.32	96.29	99	92.85	-	-
Lamtire et al.	50	71.42	66.67	83.33	50	70	-
Our study	106	91.3	57.14	93.33	50	86.79	

The specificity obtained in our study was 57.14%. This low value could be attributed to the varying experience level of the ultrasonologists involved in the study. Also, the use of ultrasound as diagnostic aid in appendicitis is associated with patient related factors such as obesity and distended gut loops in lower abdomen, which may influence the results. Gender wise analysis of negative appendectomy rate in our study showed that it was much lower in female patients (10.8%) as compared to male patients (18.9%) which is in contrast with the above-mentioned study. This is due to the fact that use of ultrasound in female patients is very helpful in ruling out other gynecologically related differential diagnoses such as adnexal pathologies which can mimic appendicitis and impose diagnostic difficulties, thus reducing the negative appendectomies in female patients.

Conclusion

The area under the curve (AUC) of the receiver operator characteristic (ROC) curve was 0.742 for the Tzanakis scoring system which was statistically significant. This study concluded that the Tzanakis scoring system is acceptable for diagnosing acute appendicitis.

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